

Modification of the Equations for the Electro-viscous Effect of Colloidal Electrolytes

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In a previous publication it has been shown how Smoluchowski's equation may be modified to account for the electro-viscous effect of colloidal electrolytes. The constants in the modified equation determined from viscosity data implicitly contained a factor, g . This point has been clarified in the present paper and it has been shown that the same equation can be derived also from Booth's equation on the basis of certain assumptions.

Some of the advantages of the modified equation and those which follow from it have been discussed.

The modified equations have been subjected to test using fresh experimental data collected from the literature and have been found satisfactory.

It has also been shown how the primary electro-viscous effect varies with the concentration of the colloidal electrolyte in the sol under different conditions.

In previous publications¹⁻³ it has been shown that λ , the specific conductivity of a solution of a colloidal electrolyte, is made up of two parts, one part $\theta\lambda_s$ contributed by the colloidal particles and another part $(1-\theta)\lambda_i$ contributed by the intermicellar solution and they are related by the equation

$$\lambda = \theta\lambda_s + (1-\theta)\lambda_i \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where θ is the fraction per unit area of an electrode (of the conductivity cell) covered by the diffuse electrical double layer of the colloidal particles and is equal to $C/(K_0 + C)$, C , the concentration (unit arbitrary) of the colloidal particles, K_0 a constant and λ_s and λ_i are proportionality constants. λ_s may be interpreted to represent the specific conductivity of the diffuse double layer associated with unit area at the plane of contact with the electrode (of the conductivity cell) and λ_i the specific conductivity of the intermicellar solution. θ may also be expressed as follows :

$$\theta = \frac{C}{K_0 + C} = \frac{C(v/V)}{K_0(v/V) + C(v/V)} = \frac{\phi}{h + \phi} \quad \dots \quad (1a)$$

where v is the volume of the colloidal particles per unit value of C and V is the volume of the colloidal solution corresponding to C so that $C(v/V) = \phi$ the volume fraction and $h = (K_0 v/V)$.

In deducing their electro-viscous equations Smoluchowski⁴ and Booth⁵ have considered the colloidal particles as non-conductors and have taken only the specific conductivity, σ of the intermicellar solution (i.e. the dispersion medium) into consideration. For a colloidal electrolyte, as discussed previously⁶⁻⁷, the specific conductivity λ of the colloidal solution should be taken into consideration. Therefore, substituting the

value of λ in place of σ in the Einstein-Smoluchowski equation and simplifying we get the following equation

$$\eta_{sp} = K\phi \left[1 + \frac{(\phi + h)}{\eta_0 a^2 (\phi \lambda_s + h \lambda_i)} \left(\frac{D\zeta}{2\pi} \right)^2 \right] \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where K is a constant equal to 2.5 for spherical particles, ζ the electrokinetic potential of the particles, a , their radius and D and η_0 the dielectric constant and viscosity of the dispersion medium. The other terms in equation (2) have the same significance as stated already.

The viscosity data of some authors^{8,9} indicate that when the product of the radius and the reciprocal of the thickness of the electrical double layer is less than 10 Smoluchowski's equation yield a value of η_{sp} higher than that observed. Therefore, for adjustment the electro-viscous portion of the equation (2) may be multiplied by a factor g and may be written as follows :

$$\eta_{sp} = K\phi \left[1 + \frac{(\phi + h)}{\eta_0 a^2 (\phi \lambda_s + h \lambda_i)} \left(\frac{D\zeta}{2\pi} \right)^2 \cdot g \right] \quad \dots \quad (2a)$$

Modification of Booth's Equation

An equation similar to (2a) can also be found from Booth's electro-viscous equation on the basis of certain assumptions. Booth's equation, when (a), ζ is less than KT/e and (b), the mobilities of the small ions are equal, may be written as follows^{5,8,9} :

$$\eta_{sp} = K\phi \left[1 + \frac{1}{\eta_0 a^2 \sigma} \left(\frac{D\zeta}{2\pi} \right)^2 \cdot g_0 \right] \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

In equation (3) $g_o = \pi(b)^2 (1+b)^2 z(b)$, $b = x/a$, x , the reciprocal of the thickness of the electrical double layer, a , the radius of the particles and $Z(b)$ the relaxation function of Booth.

If the restrictions (a) and (b) are withdrawn and the specific conductivity of the colloidal solution λ is substituted in place of σ in equation (3), then after some simplification we get the following equation

$$\eta_{sp} = K\phi \left[1 + \frac{(\phi+h)}{\eta_o a^2 (\phi\lambda_s + h\lambda_i)} \left(\frac{D\zeta}{2\pi} \right)^2 \cdot g \right] \dots (3a)$$

In equation (3a) g has been written instead of g_o since the restrictions (a) and (b) have been dropped and λ has been substituted in place of σ , it may be noted that λ is greater than σ . When the solution is extremely dilute (i.e. ϕ approaches 0) then only λ becomes equal to σ . It may also be pointed out that λ_i in the equations (2), (2a), (3a), etc. is equivalent to σ in equation (3).

To satisfy the condition that both the equations (2a) and (3a) should yield the same value of η_{sp} , g in them must be identical since each of the other terms in (2a) is equal to the corresponding term in (3a). For spherical particles equation (2a) may be written as follows :

$$\eta_{sp}/\phi = 2.5 \left[1 + \frac{A\zeta^2 g}{\lambda_s} \left(\frac{\phi+h}{\phi+h\lambda_i/\lambda_s} \right) \right] \dots (4)$$

where $A = \frac{1}{\eta_o a^2} \left(\frac{D}{2\pi} \right)^2$

Advantages of the Modified Equations

Some of the advantages of the modified equation (4) over that of Booth or Smoluchowski are indicated below :

(i) For a highly purified sol λ_i in equation (4), is much smaller than λ_s . Therefore, when ϕ is negligible compared to h , equation (4) may be written as follows :

$$\eta_{sp}/\phi = 2.5 \left[1 + \frac{A\zeta^2 gh}{\lambda_s} \left(\frac{1}{\phi+h\lambda_i/\lambda_s} \right) \right] \dots (4a)$$

If the sol is diluted maintaining pH and λ_i constant then ϕ only in equation (4a) decreases while the other terms such as ζ , λ_s etc. remain constant, so η_{sp}/ϕ should increase and this is in agreement with observation.

According to the equations of Booth or Smoluchowski when a highly purified sol is diluted keeping σ and pH constant then η_{sp}/ϕ should not change, since ζ , g etc. remain constant and this is not in agreement with observation.

(ii) Again when a neutral salt like KCl is added to the sol then λ_i in equation (4) increases sharply and with increasing concentration of KCl a condition is

soon reached when ϕ becomes negligible compared to $h\lambda_i/\lambda_s$.

Under this condition equation (4) assumes the following form

$$\eta_{sp}/\phi = 2.5 \left[1 + \frac{A\zeta^2 g}{\lambda_i} + \frac{A\zeta^2 g}{h\lambda_i} \phi \right] \dots (4b)$$

$$= 2.5 [1 + A_1 + \beta\phi] \dots (4c)$$

where $A_1 = A\zeta^2 g/\lambda_i$ and $\beta = A\zeta^2 g/h\lambda_i$

If the sol is now diluted keeping the pH and the concentration of KCl fixed then, η_{sp}/ϕ should vary linearly with ϕ . The equation of Booth or Smoluchowski does not indicate any such relationship between η_{sp}/ϕ and ϕ . It may be pointed out that here we are dealing only with the primary electro-viscous effect, since the secondary electro-viscous effect appears at a much higher value of ϕ .

(iii) It may also be noted that when the concentration of KCl added is such that $\lambda_i = \lambda_s$, then equation (4) assumes the same form as equation (3).

Verification of the Modified Equations

Stone-Masui and Watilon⁹ have investigated the electro-viscous properties of monodisperse polystyrene lattices prepared by emulsion polymerisation using Na-stearate and Na-dodecylsulphate as emulsifiers. The particles are spherical in shape and the data recorded in the Tables I, II and V and Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 of their paper have been used in the tables 1 and 2 of this paper.

In table 1 the variation of η_{sp}/ϕ with dilution by water of the pure sol stabilised by Na-stearate is recorded. In column 1 under the head miscellaneous, the equation used and the value of the constants in it have been indicated. The constants have been determined from the experimental data. The diameter of the particles have been represented by d .

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF η_{sp}/ϕ OF THE PURE SOL WITH DILUTION BY WATER AT 25°C.

Miscellaneous	ϕ	Values of η_{sp}/ϕ	
		Observed	Calculated
Eq ⁿ . (4a)	Lt $\phi \rightarrow 0$		34.5
$A\zeta^2 g h/\lambda_s = 1.205$	0.0016	33.7	33.9
	0.0086	31.5	31.8
$h\lambda_i/\lambda_s = 0.945$	0.0092	30.1	30.6
	0.0145	30.0	30.2
$d = 50 \text{ m}\mu$	0.0213	29.7	28.5

TABLE 2—EXPERIMENTAL VALUES OF $(\eta_{sp}/\phi)_{\phi \rightarrow 0}$ OF THE SOLS WITH ELECTROLYTE

Emulsifier	System	d in $m\mu$	Composition millimoles/L	pH	Experimental $K = (\eta_{sp}/\phi)_{\phi \rightarrow 0}$	Constants in eq ⁿ , (4c) A_1	$\frac{4c}{\beta}$
Na-stearate	1	70	0.1 HClO ₄	4	2.5	very small	128
„	2	70	{ 0.1 HClO ₄ + 0.1 NaClO ₄	4	2.5	very small	69
„	3	56	0.1 NaOH	10	3.6	0.44	238
„	4	63	0.05 NaClO ₄	6	5.1	1.04	428
„	5	50	0.1 NaClO ₄	6	3.7	0.48	169
„	6	50	0.1 KClO ₄	6	3.3	0.32	175
„	7	63	0.2 NaClO ₄	6	2.8	0.12	79
Na-dodecyl-sulphate	8	56	0.1 HClO ₄	4	3.5	0.4	560

TABLE 3—VARIATION OF (η_{sp}/ϕ) WITH KNO₃ CONCENTRATION AT 20.5°

Equation and constants	S	BC	R	Values of $(\eta_{sp}/\phi)_s$		
				Observed	Calculated from Booth's eq ⁿ . f (1+BC)	Author's eq ⁿ . 6.73 R
Booth's eq ⁿ f=3.75	0.0	0.294	1.0	6.73	4.85	6.73
	0.0005	0.207	0.695	4.64	4.53	4.66
	0.001	0.131	0.633	4.26	4.24	4.26
Author's eq ⁿ . (5)	0.002	0.083	0.595	4.10	4.06	4.00
m=0.454	0.003	0.075	0.580	3.88	4.03	3.90
m _o =0.000243	0.005	0.075	0.567	3.88	4.03	3.81
	0.01	0.062	0.557	3.88	3.98	3.75

In table 2 under the head composition are recorded the final concentrations in millimoles per liter of the electrolytes added to the sol. In column 3 of the table, d represents the diameter in $m\mu$ of the particles of the different sols or systems. At each electrolyte concentration mentioned in the table, η_{sp}/ϕ of the sol varies linearly with ϕ .

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table 1 that (η_{sp}/ϕ) of the pure sol increases as it is diluted with water. The values of (η_{sp}/ϕ) calculated from equation (4a) agree well with those observed so long as ϕ is less than 0.0213 and can be neglected compared to the constant (a $\zeta^2 g h/\lambda_s$). The value of $(\eta_{sp}/\phi)_{\phi \rightarrow 0}$ is 34.5 and hence the electro-viscous effect is equal to 32.0 which is quite high.

All the systems in table 2 contain added electrolyte and their (η_{sp}/ϕ) varies linearly with ϕ . The linear

variation is represented by the modified equation (4c) written as follows :

$$(\eta_{sp}/\phi) = 2.5\beta\phi + 2.5(1 + A_1) \quad \dots (4c)$$

It will be noticed from the data recorded in table 2 that only in the systems 1 and 2, A_1 is negligible compared to unity and consequently the experimental $K=2.5$. The electrolyte added to system 1 is HClO₄ and the pH of the sol is 4.0. Since the particles of the sol are negatively charged the pH near their surface must be lower still. Under this condition the dissociation of the potential determining ion containing carboxyl group is much suppressed. Therefore, the value of ζ must be small and that of λ_s high, since the H⁺ ions have high mobility, so that A_1 becomes negligible compared to unity. For the same reason A_1 in system 2 becomes negligible compared to unity since not only HClO₄ but NaClO₄ have also been added to it.

In system 8 the potential determining ion is a strong electrolyte and so ζ is not much lowered by the addition of HClO_4 . Therefore, A_1 is not negligible and so the experimental $K=2.5 (1 + 0.4) = 3.5$.

It may be pointed out that electrolyte content of system 4 is the lowest. The value of ζ of this system should, therefore, be quite high and that of λ_i quite low and so A_1 should be high. In agreement with this conclusion A_1 has been found to be 1.04 and the experimental K equal to $2.5 (1 + 1.04)$ or 5.1 the highest recorded in table 2.

It is to be noted that only primary electro-viscous effect is operating in the range of values of ϕ considered in the tables 1 and 2.

Variation of η_{sp}/ϕ with electrolyte concentration at constant ϕ .

Rutgers and Nagels⁹ have subjected Booth's equation (3) to test under conditions in which ϕ remains constant but the concentration of the added electrolyte varies, using an AgI sol, the particles of which are spherical in shape and have radius equal to 6×10^{-6} cm.

Starting from equation (2) and assuming linear variation of ζ and λ_i with the concentration (say upto 20 millimoles per liter) of the added electrolyte, the following equation has been deduced by the author in a previous publication¹⁰

$$R = (\eta_{sp}/\phi)_s / (\eta_{sp}/\phi)_o = \left(1 - \frac{mS}{m_o + S}\right) \dots (5)$$

$$\text{Therefore, } (\eta_{sp}/\phi)_s = R(\eta_{sp}/\phi)_o = \left(1 - \frac{mS}{m_o + S}\right) (\eta_{sp}/\phi)_o \quad (5a)$$

where $(\eta_{sp}/\phi)_s$ and $(\eta_{sp}/\phi)_o$ represent respectively the reduced viscosity of the sol with and without added electrolyte, m and m_o are constants and S denotes the concentration in moles per liter of the added electrolyte. In the deduction of equation (5) the factor g has been dropped but linear variations of ζ and λ_i with S have been introduced to account for the observed variation of (η_{sp}/ϕ) .

In table 3 are recorded the data of Rutgers and Nagels⁹. They have written Booth's equation as follows :

$$(\eta_{sp}/\phi) = f(1 + BC)$$

where f = the Einstein constant K , $B = \frac{1}{\eta_o a^2 \sigma} \left(\frac{D\xi}{2\pi}\right)^2$

and $C = \pi(b)^2 Z(b) (1 + b)^2$ in which b is the same as in equation (3) and $Z(b)$, the Booth relaxation function. S in table 3 represents the concentration of KNO_3 in moles per liter and the other terms have the same significance as stated already.

In table 4 are recorded the data of Briggs¹¹ on the variation of η_{sp} of sodium gum arabate with the concentration of NaCl added at constant C and at 25°.

TABLE 4—VARIATION OF (η_{sp}/C) WITH THE CONCENTRATION S OF NaCl AT 25°.

Miscellaneous	S	η_{sp}	Values of R	
			Observed	Calculated
C=0.25	0.0	0.511	1.0	1.0
Eq ⁿ (5)	0.001	0.214	0.419	0.417
m=0.866	0.002	0.155	0.303	0.303
$m_o = 0.000485$	0.005	0.108	0.212	0.211
	0.01	0.089	0.174	0.174
C=0.375	0.0	0.700	1.0	1.0
Eq ⁿ (5)	0.001	0.345	0.493	0.498
m=0.868	0.002	0.255	0.364	0.364
$m_o = 0.00073$	0.005	0.171	0.244	0.243
	0.01	0.134	0.191	0.191
C=0.5	0.0	0.892	1.0	1.0
Eq ⁿ (5)	0.0005	0.637	0.714	0.708
m=0.848	0.001	0.505	0.566	0.565
$m_o = 0.00095$	0.002	0.375	0.420	0.425
	0.004	0.284	0.318	0.315
	0.008	0.212	0.238	0.242
	0.012	0.187	0.210	0.214
C=0.75	0.0	1.118	1.0	1.0
Eq ⁿ (5)	0.001	0.789	0.696	0.683
m=0.825	0.002	0.612	0.547	0.542
$m_o = 0.0016$	0.905	0.408	0.365	0.376
	0.01	0.316	0.283	0.289
C=1.0	0.0	1.512	1.0	1.0
Eq ⁿ (5)	0.0005	1.242	0.823	0.832
m=0.0843	0.001	1.088	0.720	0.720
$m_o = 0.00201$	0.002	0.865	0.572	0.580
	0.005	0.602	0.398	0.399
	0.01	0.454	0.300	0.298
	0.02	0.355	0.235	0.237

Under the head miscellaneous in column 1 are mentioned the concentration, C of Na-gum arabate in grams per 100 ml. of the sol and the values of the constants m and m_o in equation (5). The other terms in the table have the same significance as stated already.

In table 5 are recorded the values of m_o and C collected from table 4. m_o occurs in equation (5) and C denotes the concentration in gram of the colloidal electrolyte per 100 ml of the sol. The relation between them is discussed in the next section.

TABLE 5—VARIATION OF m_o WITH C, THE CONCENTRATION OF COLLOID.

Miscellaneous	C	Values of m_o from	
		Table—4	Equation (6)
Equation (6)	0.25	0.000485	0.00051
$K_1 = 0.002$	0.375	0.00073	0.00076
	0.50	0.00095	0.00101
$K_2 = 1 \times 10^{-5}$	0.75	0.00160	0.00151
	1.0	0.00201	0.00201

The data recorded in table 3 on the variation of η_{sp}/ϕ with the concentration S of KNO_3 , at constant ϕ , fit the author's equation (5) better than Booth's equation even when f is put equal to 3.75 instead of 2.5. It may be that the values of ζ used by Rutgers and Nagels in Booth's equation are not correct. Chan and Goring¹² have also observed significant difference between the experimental results and those calculated using Booth's equation (3).

It is also evident from table 4 that the observed variation of R with the concentration S of NaCl agrees

well with that calculated from equation (5). An examination of the data in this table also shows that m_o of equation (5) increases as C, the concentration of Na-gum arabate increases. It follows from the deduction¹⁰ of equation (5) that

$$m_o = \frac{C\lambda_s + K_o\lambda_i}{K_o\lambda_i h} = K_1 C + K_2 \quad \dots (6)$$

where $K_1 = \lambda_s/K_o\lambda_i h$, $K_2 = \frac{1}{h}$ and $h = \frac{1}{\lambda_i} \left(\frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial S} \right)$; λ_i as

stated already represents the specific conductivity of the intermicellar solution without added electrolyte (i.e. $S=0$). Under the experimental conditions adopted by Briggs¹¹. K_1 , K_2 and h remain constant and so m_o should vary linearly with C. The data recorded in table 5 confirm this conclusion.

References

1. B. N. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 359.
2. B. N. GHOSH, *Proc. Indian Nat. Sci. Acad.*, 1972, A30, 45.
3. B. N. GHOSH, *A.C.S. Symposium Series, Colloid Dispersions and Micellar Behaviour*, 1975, 9, 316.
4. M. VON. SMOLUCHOWSKI, *Kolloid Z.*, 1916, 18, 190.
5. F. BOOTH, *Proc. Roy. Soc. (London)*, 1950, A203, 533.
6. B. N. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 881.
7. B. N. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 1066.
8. A. G. RUTGERS AND P. NAGELS, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1958, 13, 149.
9. J. STONE-MASUI AND A. WATILON, *J. Colloid and Interface Sci.*, 1968, 28, 187.
10. B. N. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 255.
11. D. R. BRIGGS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1941, 45, 866.
12. F. S. CHAN AND D. A. I. GORING, *J. Colloid and Interface Sci.* 1966, 22, 371.